

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R9.5 Communication Plan

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1 INTRODUCTION

The R9.5 Communication Plan output was created in cooperation with project partners. The Communication Plan contains a list of planned communication and dissemination activities. Two main and ten other results of the project have been defined, including delivery deadlines. All project partners will be involved.

2 OBJECTIVE

The main aim of project communication and dissemination activities is to create awareness of the existence of the project, disseminate project results to identified target groups to achieve the planned impact, raise general awareness of CCS as an important climate change mitigation technology and highlight the bilateral Czech-Norwegian cooperation based on project funding from Norway Grants.

3 TARGET GROUP

Eight main stakeholder target groups have been identified:

- A. Industrial stakeholders interested in reducing their CO₂ emissions by means of CCS – this is a national group, representing mainly emission-intensive industries like iron & steel production, cement works, heat and combined heat & power production, waste incinerators, etc. They are expected to use project results to assess the role CCS can play in their emission reduction strategy and possibly use the opportunity to cooperate on the development of a CCS pilot project. Outcomes of the dialog with this group can be further extended to elsewhere in Europe, as many of the industrial players operate on the global market
- B. Industrial stakeholders – possible vendors of CCS-related equipment, services and technologies – this group can be international, involving companies from the Czech Republic, Norway and elsewhere. This group would be interested in providing their products and services to the expected follow-up CCS activities (pilot and demonstration projects) that would be based on project results.
- C. Policy makers and regulators of CO₂ emission reduction policies, CCS and CO₂ storage in the Czech Republic – especially responsible Czech ministries (Ministry of Environment, Ministry of Economy and Trade and the Czech Mining Authority as the most important regulatory body. They are expected to use project results as an evidence of technical viability of CO₂ geological storage on the territory of Czechia as a crucial step for the deployment of the CCS technology in the country. This would strengthen the role of CCS as a climate change mitigation option in the national decarbonisation strategy. In addition, project results will provide important input and practical experience for fine-tuning of the national regulatory framework for future CO₂ storage projects.
- D. International CCS research community is an important target group with regard to international confrontation and benchmarking of the quality of performed research and the achieved results. This group is also expected to provide feedback to project results presented on the international forum in form of conference presentations and scientific publications.

- E. CCS stakeholder community in Norway – a special target group related to the Donor State that needs to be informed about the project and its results to demonstrate the effect of bilateral Czech-Norwegian cooperation and investment of Norwegian tax-payers' money. In addition, project results will open additional opportunities for future bilateral activities in the CCS area. Project findings, especially subsurface studies and optimisation can also be used to improve understanding of CO₂ injection in the North Sea.
- F. Students of geosciences and climate change-related programmes need to be approached to ensure future development of CCS, in the sense of both preparing the new generation of professionals to implement the technology and delivering the proper information to future decision makers and influencers.
- G. Journalists and media are an important target to group to achieve widespread dissemination of information on the project and its results. Scientific journalists in Czechia will be approached to deliver the defined messages to the interested part of general public.

General public and NGOs. They will be approached with the objective to explain the importance of CCS technology, raise the awareness of its existence and provide information about the activities performed by project partners within the project and other CCS-related activities. Increased public awareness and basic knowledge related to CCS technology might lower the intensity of possible public resistance to locating of future storage sites.

4 MESSAGES

The messages and subjects to be communicated can be divided into three main categories:

1. Information about the existence of the project, its aim, objectives, bilateral Czech-Norwegian cooperation and Norway Grants funding (to reach all target groups)
2. Project results and achievements in detail (targeting mainly groups A-D)
3. Information about the broader context of the project and its achievements, including the role of CCS technology (targeting mainly groups C and E-H)

project funded from the KAPPA programme. The conference is expected to be an international platform with an active involvement of our Norwegian partners and experts from other countries (such as Poland, Slovakia, etc.). Invitations to attend the conference will be sent to members of all project target groups, except for general public.

Website

A Project website in both Czech and English will be created (result R9.8), offering two main parts – public and internal. The public part will offer information on the CO₂-SPICER project itself, project news, results, achievements and activities connected with the project, including, for instance, announcements of project events and presentations held at these events. The website will also offer a link to special information portal dedicated to the CCS technology, operated by CGS since 2006 at <http://www.geology.cz/ccs>. The portal will continue bringing up-to-date information on CCS and its development from within the Czech Republic and abroad; the educational section will be updated during the CO₂-SPICER project, taking the latest developments of the technology into account.

All project partners will post information about their involvement in the project, important project news and a link to the project website on their institutional websites.

CLIMIT Summit

The CLIMIT Summit in Oslo in early 2021 will represent an excellent opportunity to make the Norwegian CCS community aware of project existence and its objectives. The next edition in 2023 will already provide opportunity to present project results.

International conferences

International CCS-related conferences are the best opportunity to present the project and its results to the international research community and CCS professionals, as well as to get valuable feedback on the quality of the research performed. The targeted high-level events where presentation of project results is planned are the Trondheim CCS Conferences in June 2021 and 2023, the top international CCS event – the GHGT-16 conference in autumn 2022 (location still unknown) and the traditional CO₂GeoNet Open Forum organized in Venice annually in April-May.

Possibilities of organising additional activities (e.g. targeted workshops) attached to these events will be examined in cooperation with the other CCS project funded by the KAPPA programme, using possible additional funding from the Bilateral Fund of EEA/Norway Grants.

In addition to the above events, it is expected that project results and achievements will be presented at other international professional seminars, workshops and conferences that will take place within project duration.

National events

Opportunities will be sought to approach national CCS stakeholders in both the Czech Republic and Norway at suitable national events in both countries by presenting the project and its results. These can be of different focus, ranging from CCS and geo-energy, through energy transition, emission-intensive industries to decarbonisation strategies and climate change mitigation. The list will also include possible events organized by the Programme Operator or the National Focal Point.

End-User Club

Representatives of the main project target groups – industrial companies interested in the CCS technology, policy makers and regulators - will be invited to join the project End-User Group (part of WP10). The participation will provide them the opportunity to closely follow the project development, get first-hand access to the results and interact with the project team. At the same time, the End-user Group will also serve as the Project's main advisory body. Some of these stakeholders already expressed their willingness to get involved in End-User Group – for instance the Czech Ministry of the Environment, the Czech Ministry of Industry and Trade and Liberty (a leading Czech steelmaking company). Other potential members will be approached during the first period of the Project. Two to three joint meetings of the Management Board and the End-User Group are planned to take place over the duration of the Project with the aim of presenting the current Project results and obtaining valuable feedback from stakeholders on the progress and future practical applicability of its results; online communication tools will be used between the meetings.

Bilateral consultations

In addition to the invitation to the End-User Club, bilateral consultations (including in-house) will be offered to end-users of project results. Their aim will be to present the project, its results and discuss possibilities of utilizing CCS as a decarbonisation measure on both company, industry and national levels in more detail.

Lectures

Lectures for students informing about the project and its results in the framework of general presentation of the CCS technology will be held at leading Czech universities, and possibilities will be sought to give lectures in the framework of various science-popularisation activities (e.g. Week of Science).

Publications in scientific journals

The results of the project will be published in domestic and international journals. Four articles in leading peer-reviewed journals have been planned as Main results (results No. TO01000112-V9-11, type J) and are expected to be published within project duration. In addition, a research article presenting the main results of the project will be prepared in spring 2024 and submitted to an impacted peer-reviewed journal with the outlook to publication later in 2024, after the official end of the project (result No. TO01000112-V8 - type O with prospect to change into type Jimp). The Open Science principles and provisions will be respected at all publishing activities.

Final technical project report

The project final technical report will be prepared with support of the CGS Publishing department in “publication quality” (in terms of language, layout, etc.), will be printed in a limited number of copies (up to 50) and distributed to main target group members (participants of the End-User Group, ministries, industry representatives, etc. - result No TO01000112-V7, type O).

Popular science journal article

An article in one of the leading Czech popular scientific journals (e.g. Vesmír) will be prepared by CGS in 2023 (result R9.10).

Newsletters

CGS supported by other project partners will produce 3 issues of project newsletter, in both printed and electronic version (result R9.11). The newsletter will target Czech stakeholders and will be prepared in Czech language. The tentative release dates are 12/2021, 2/2023 and 4/2024.

Press releases

CGS will prepare two press releases for the media (result R9.7) – one in the beginning and one at the end of the project. They will be distributed using the established communication channels of CGS and all project partners.

Social media news

CGS will inform about the project in social media – the Czech geological Facebook channel “Svět geologie” and the Geology TV YouTube channel.

6 ORGANISATION AND RESOURCES

Communication and dissemination activities will be organised in a dedicated Work Package (WP9), led by CGS. WP leader will at the same time act as the project Communication Manager. All project partners will be involved. Two main and ten other results of the project have been defined for this WP, including delivery deadlines – see below:

Tab. 6-1: Project results.

Main results		
ID	Description	Deadline
TO01000112-V7	Final technical report of the CO ₂ -SPICER project (type O)	4/2024
TO01000112-V8	Manuscript of article showcasing CO ₂ -SPICER project results submitted for publication in a peer-reviewed journal (type O)	4/2024
Other results		
ID	Description	Deadline
R9.3	Project launch event	12/2020
R9.4	Project graphic style package	12/2020
R9.5	Updated Communication plan	11/2020, 10/2022
R9.6	Project information leaflet	12/2020
R9.7	Press releases	12/2020, 4/2024
R9.8	Project website in CZ and EN	1/2021
R9.9	Posters, oral presentations and abstracts published in proceedings at national and international events – track record on project website	Ongoing, final version 4/2024
R9.10	Article in popular science journal	10/2023
R9.11	Project newsletter – 3 issues	12/2021, 2/2023, 4/2024

R9.12	Czech-Norwegian CCS workshop held in Norway	2/2024
R9.13	Final project conference	4/2024

The activities will be funded from the dedicated WP9 budget and resources that include 52.5 person-months of workload by project partners and 1.496 mil. CZK of other costs. The detailed budget breakdown is provided in the Detailed description of Work Packages (Attachment 6 to Partnership Agreement) – description of WP9. The budget has been carefully planned and its level corresponds to the high ambitions of the Communication plan.

7 EVALUATION

The following evaluation indicators to assess the performance of CO2-SPICER communication activities have been defined:

Tab. 7-1: Evaluation indicators.

Indicator	Target value
Number of participants of the Launch event	30
Number of participants of Czech-Norwegian CCS workshop in Norway	20
Number of participants of Final project conference	60
Number of newsletters published	3
Number of CCS-related events where project information and results are presented	6
Number of peer-reviewed publications achieved	4
Number of End-User Club meetings	2
Number of Main and Other results of WP9 delivered on time	9

Evaluation indicators and their fulfilment will be continuously monitored by WP9 leader and reported in annual periodic reports to TACR.

Communication Manager

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More information about the project can be found at
co2-spicer.geology.cz.

PROJECT PARTNERS

COORDINATOR

Programme **Kappa**

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